

PALABRIA Project: Supporting Students to Improve their Writing Skills with Generative AI and Learning Analytics

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Abstract

PALABRIA project is an interdisciplinary project that aims to support students in their language use using Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Learning Analytics. In order to do that, several common complex linguistic errors are identified and different AI techniques are analyzed to detect and correct errors. Moreover, a web application is designed so that students can interact with it to detect the errors, and get some metrics and visualizations obtained using LA with data about their activity and errors when interacting with the platform. In addition, the web application is designed to provide personalized feedback. Finally, some pilots are also proposed to evaluate the proposed solutions.

Keywords

Generative Artificial Intelligence, Linguistics, Language Learning, Learning Analytics

1. Introduction

Language is crucial among students to communicate their work, and they need to develop proper linguistic skills for their professional life. However, it is very frequent that they have errors even when they are native speakers. For example, inappropriate use of register, use of gerunds, discursive markers, prepositions, etc. In order to avoid language errors, students might use Generative AI (GenAI) to check their documents, but the direct use of GenAI tools might be limited because GenAI might not detect complex errors beyond grammar, and their feedback might be more limited. For instance, one key missing element is the analytics. In Learning Analytics (LA), it is possible to analyze students' behaviors and generate learning indicators and visualizations about their progress. Similarly, it is possible to use LA to generate indicators about how students write and their most frequent errors. This way, it is also possible to generate feedback at both text and global level, i.e., feedback about each text the student generates, and global feedback with recommendations about how to improve language errors based on all the texts the student has submitted to the platform. With this idea, PALABRIA project (<https://palabria.uc3m.es/>) aims to use Artificial Intelligence (AI) to detect and correct language errors, use LA to make students aware of their errors, and provide personalized feedback to support them. This project is a 2.5-year interdisciplinary project (July 2024-December 2026) that joins efforts of a linguistic

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team from the Department of Humanities: Philosophy, Language and Literature, and a technological team from the Department of Telematics Engineering at Universidad Carlos III de Madrid.

2. Objectives

The objectives of the project are as follows:

- O1: Develop a research framework comprising: 1) a state-of-the-art review of AI for language error detection; 2) a pedagogical model emphasizing AI to support students and teachers; 3) a set of scenarios to analyze the potential of IA to detect language errors and provide feedback; and 4) the definition of research instruments for evaluating and developing pilot experiences.
- O2: Design and develop AI solutions to enhance language support for Spanish users. This objective comprises: 1) analysis of current GenAI solutions to detect language errors and provide feedback; 2) development of a system that combines AI (e.g., using machine learning, generative AI, etc.) and linguistic rules for detecting errors in written language; 3) development of an AI-powered LA system to detect discourse or writing characteristics of students and provide analytics or predictions about their language performance; and 4) development of an adaptive system, including AI, to provide personalized feedback to students on their formal language use.
- O3: Define a technological and linguistic framework consisting of: 1) analyzing and selecting existing AI technologies to detect and correct errors in written language; 2) defining specific linguistic rules and common language problems to be addressed, and 3) proposing technical requirements and the architecture of the system including the solutions proposed in O2.
- O4: Design, implement, and evaluate pilot experiences in real-world contexts based on the project's results (particularly objectives O2 and O3).

In order to carry out this project, a Design Science Research Methodology is proposed, so that systems can be implemented and redefined progressively with feedback from the stakeholders.

3. Current status and expected impact

In this project, several linguistic errors were initially defined for the analyses. Currently, work has focused on “impersonal tú” and gerund of posteriority. With these errors, several AI techniques, including GenAI with Mistral and Llama, has been used to detect and correct the errors. With the best performing model (Mistral), a web application was developed so that students could interact. In this application, students can upload a PDF or input raw text and the application provides a corrected version, an explanatory feedback of the errors, and it allows students to edit the output. Metrics include the number of detected errors, length, and number of edits by AI and the students. In addition, it includes an analytics module with global metrics on platform use and frequency of errors in multiple documents. It also includes global feedback with recommendations to improve the language based on the frequency of errors. With this tool, an evaluation has been carried out on the accuracy of the detection and correction, as well as the feedback, which was reviewed by three experts. Moreover, two pilots have been carried out with students implementing detectors of more basic errors based on linguistic rules, and with students downloading the code of the tool and extending it with new features. Future work should focus on evaluating the tool with students and extending the analytics capability and the range of detected errors. The project can have a significant impact on students and research on language detection and LA. For the moment, current publications (available on the project website) and the PALABRIA conference, hosted in April 2026, show the potential of the proposed solutions.

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